

Effects of the Processing Parameters on Pultrusion Process

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ABSTRACT

Pultrusion process is a continuous processing technique for fabricating fiber reinforced polymer composite. The major parameters which affect the pultrusion process include the viscosities, curing kinetic constants and preheat temperature of resin, geometry and temperature distribution of die, and the pulling rate, etc. This paper discusses the effects of processing parameters on the carbon and glass fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester and epoxy composites. In this study, viscosities of resins at various temperatures were measured and the optimum preheat temperature of resin was investigated. A dynamic scanning differential calorimeter was used to determine the exothermic heat and the curing kinetics of resin. A finite difference method was utilized to simulate the temperature distribution and the conversion of resin along the die during the processing.

1. INTRODUCTION

For the past years, a number of articles(1-10) have illustrated the processing, applications and properties of pultruded products. Very recently, several researchers(11-17) have discussed the processing variables and developed some mathematical models to simulate the process. Jones(11) and Price(13), et al, had analyzed the origins of the pulling force in a pultrusion die. Han, et al,(16) had simulated the temperature distribution in the die and the conversion of resin versus die position at different pulling speed. However,

very few paper investigate the effects of resin viscosity, die temperature and pulling rate on the processing and on the properties of pultruded products. Furthermore, the mathematical model which predicts the temperature profiles and the conversion of resin in pultrusion process has to be verified by comparing with experimental results.

In order to manufacture pultruded products with consistent quality, one must understand the characteristics and the reaction temperature of resin during the processing, and then select the proper processing conditions for the process. In this research the changing of viscosity with time at different preheat temperatures of resin was studied. The simulation of curing temperature at various die temperatures, and pulling rates was investigated. The simulated data has been compared with experimental results data to verify the prediction of the model proposed.

2. APPARATUS AND MATERIALS

2.1. Apparatus

The pultrusion equipment used in this research has been described in the previous paper(18). A pultrusion die with the dimension of 0.208 x 1.27 x 82cm.(thickness x width x length) was used in this study and is illustrated in Figure 1.. The surfaces of this stainless steel die have been treated by chrome plating. Viscosities of resin were measured at various temperatures for different times with a Brookfield RVF model viscometer. Kinetic constants were obtained by a PERKIN ELMER Differential Scanning Calorimeter DSC-2 and an IBM personal computer.

Figure 1. Pultrusion Die With Multiple Heating Zones

2.2 Materials

Table 1. summarizes the materials used in this study;

which include isophthalic-based unsaturated polyester resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) type epoxy resin, curing agent, accelerator, filler, glass fiber, carbon fiber, low profile additive and mold release agent.

TABLE 1
Materials Used for This Study

(1) Resin	Unsaturated Polyester $\eta=750$ cps Isophthalic $\rho=1.12$ Based (UP)	ESTERSET 2832 ETERHAL CHEN. Co., Taiwan, R.O.C.
	Diglycidyl Ether of $\eta=9,000-$ Bisphenol-A Epoxy (EP) 14,000 cps EEW=182-194 $\rho=1.16$	EPON 828 SHELL CO., U.S.A.
(2) Curing Agent	Benzyl Peroxide	INTEROX CHEN. PLY. LTD., U.S.A.
	Nadic Methyl $\eta=175-275$ cps Anhydride $\rho=1.20-1.25$	HY-906 Ciba-Geigy, Switzerland
(3) Accelerator	Benzyl Dimethyl Amine $\rho=0.90$	DY-062 Ciba-Geigy, Switzerland
	2-Ethyl 4-Methyl Imidazole	2E4MZ Curezol CO., Japan
(4) Filler	Calcium Carbonate $\rho=2.7$	Yin-Chin, CHEM. CO., Taiwan, R.O.C.
(5) Fiber	Glass Fiber for UP $\rho=2.54$ E-glass	1064-NT-15, PPG. IND. INC U.S.A.
	Carbon Fiber for EP $\rho=1.77$	HTA-12000, TOHO, Japan
(6) Low Profile	PVAc $\eta=5,000$ cps SM content 60% $\rho=0.997$	LP-40A, U.C.C., U.S.A.
(7) Mold Release Agent	for UP	Zelec UN Du Pont, U.S.A.
	for EP	INT-1854, AXEL, U.S.A.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The Effect of Resin Viscosity

In a pultrusion process, if the viscosity of resin is too low, the excessive drainage of resin will cause the pultruded part to have an insufficient resin content and a sloughed surface. However, if the viscosity is too high, the viscous drag of resin at the preform section may break the filament and may cause poor fiber wet-out. Hence, the viscosity of resin has to be determined before processing. Experimental results indicate that the viscosity of unsaturated polyester at the ranges from 650 cps to 2,500 cps is suitable for this study. As shown in Figure 2., the viscosities of unsaturated polyester resin varied with time at different temperatures. Although the proper preheat temperature of unsaturated polyester resin is from 30-50°C, 50°C is more suitable for processing. This is because the higher the preheat temperature the shorter the reaction time will be and the temperature difference between the surface and the core of the pultruded materials will be less. Furthermore, a short reaction time will increase the production rate, and the lowered temperature difference may avoid the thermal stress induced cracking.

Figure 3. illustrates that the viscosity of epoxy varies with time at different temperatures. At a temperature below 30°C, the viscosity of epoxy is too high to be operated. While above 60°C, the viscosity is too low to be handled. Consequently, the preheat temperature of resin may be set at 40-50°C to insure a proper operation condition.

Figure 2. Viscosity of Unsaturated Polyester Resin versus Time

Figure 3. Viscosity of Epoxy resin versus Time

3.2. Reaction Kinetics

A dynamic method of Differential Scanning Calorimetry was used to determine the exothermic heat and curing kinetics of resin. The weight of sample used in the DSC cell was 5-10mg.; the heating rate of DSC was 10°C/min.. The base line was obtained by studying the sample at the same condition as above. The rate of heat generated, dH/dt ; and the heat capacity, C_p , were calibrated by Indium and Sapphire. An autocatalytic kinetic model as described in Equation(1) was used to express the reaction kinetics of resin.

$$dX/dt = K_0 \cdot \exp(-E/RT)(1-X)^n X^m \quad (1)$$

(symbols and notations are listed in Table 2.)

It is assumed that the reaction rate, dX/dt , is directly proportional to the rate of heat generated, dH/dt . According to this assumption the conversion of resin, X , and the reaction rate, dX/dt , can be obtained.

The kinetic parameters were obtained by substituting the variables T , X and dX/dt into Equation(1) and utilizing a linear regression computer program. Results are listed in Table 3. The calculated kinetic parameters of unsaturated polyester and epoxy resin agree very well with experimental DSC data as shown in Figures 4. and 5.

TABLE 2
Symbols and Notations

ρ	: density (g/cm)
C_p	: specific heat (cal./°C)
K_0	: thermal conductivity (cal./cm.sec.°K)
w	: weight fraction (%)
X	: conversion (%)
K_a	: Arrhenius equation prefactor
E	: activity energy (cal./g)
R	: gas constant (J./g°K)
T	: reaction temperature (°K)
t	: time (sec.)
n, m	: kinetic exponents
R_a	: reaction rate (1/sec.)
V_z	: pulling rate (cm./min.)
Z	: pulling direction distance (cm.)
Y	: thickness direction distance (cm.)
ΔH	: exothermic heat of reaction (cal./g)

3.3. Heat Transfer In The Die

Heat transfer in the die during the pultrusion is expressed in Equation(2), which was solved by a finite difference method:

$$\rho \cdot V_z \cdot C_p \cdot dT/dz = k \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial Y^2} \right) + W \cdot \Delta H \cdot dX/dt \quad (2)$$

(physical properties of the materials are summarized in Table

Figure 4. Conversion of Unsaturated Polyester Resin versus Temperature

Figure 5. The Conversion of Epoxy Resin versus Temperature

3.)

Figure 6. illustrates the temperature distribution and the conversion of resin versus die distance. The curves shown in Figure 6. express the simulated temperature distributions (curves 1., 2. and 4.) and the conversions of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy system (curves 5. and 6.) at various die thickness positions from the die wall. The curve 3. in Figure 6. summarizes the experimental data and represents the temperature profile of resin measured at the position of 0.080 cm. from the die wall. One can observe that the results match very well with the simulated curves.

Figure 7. shows the distribution of reaction temperature and the conversion of unsaturated polyester. In a pultrusion process, the higher the die temperature used, the faster the pulling rate shall be. However, decomposition and cracking may occur on the surface of the pultruded part due to the high die

TABLE 3
Properties of Resins for This Study

Resin	Unsaturated Polyester	Epoxy
Composition Weight Ratio, (phr)	2832/BPO/CaCO ₃ /LP-40A 100/ 2/ 5/ 5	828/NMA/2E4MZ/BDMA 100/ 90/ 1.5/ 1
Total Heat of Cure, (cal/g)	74.8	65.8
DSC on-set Temp., T _i (°C)	90	97.5
DSC Peak Temp., T _m (°C)	117	131.3
DSC Complete Temp., T _s (°C)	150	170
Specific Heat, C _{pr} (cal/g°C) C _{pm} (cal/g°C)	0.50 0.30	0.35 0.2+2.7x10 ⁻⁴ T
Thermal Conductivity K _r (cal/cm sec °C) K _m (cal/cm sec °C)	4.05x10 ⁻⁴ 5.5 x10 ⁻⁴	3.9x10 ⁻⁴ 5.0x10 ⁻⁴
Density, ρ _r (g/cm ³) ρ _m (g/cm ³)	1.11 1.235 ^a	1.15 1.18 ^b

a. Curing cycle : 70°C/1hr +100°C/1hr +150°C/2hr

b. Curing cycle : 70°C/1hr +120°C/1hr +180°C/4hr

Figure 6. Temperature Distribution and Conversion of Resin versus Die Distance

Figure 7. Temperature Distribution and Conversion of Resin versus Die Distance.

Figure 8. Temperature Distribution and Conversion of Resin versus Die Distance.

Figure 9. Temperature Distribution and Conversion of Resin versus Die Distance.

temperature. Hence, a proper setting of die temperature is the key for a successful pultrusion process. Comparing Figures 8. and 6., one can find that the reaction rate in Figure 8. is faster and the conversion of resin is more complete than those in Figure 6. Actually, the process condition in Figure 8. is the same as in Figure 6.; except the die temperature sets in Figure 8. are higher; especially, at the positions of 5 cm. to 30 cm. and of 50 cm. to 82 cm. from the entrance.

It is worth noting in pultrusion industry that a consistent quality of products is even more important than a high production rate. Sometimes, when applying an undrsiably high die temperature, the viscosity of resin at the front of die is low which will cause backflow of resin and an insufficient resin content or a sloughed surface in the product.

As indicated by Jones(19) an incompletely cured product may exist when the conversion of resin is less than 80%. But in pultrusion process it is not required that the resin has to be completely cured for pultruding a part out of the die. It is only necessary that the resin is hard enough to maintain its shape after being pultruded, the resin then can be fully cured by a postcure treatment. The processing condition in Figure 9.is the same as in Figure 6., except that the pulling speed is increased from 64 cm./min. to 85.5 cm./min.. Comparing these two figures, one can see that the faster the pulling rate, the lower the conversion of resin. However, when the conversion of too low, a sloughed surface may occur.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, glass fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester and carbon fiber reinforced epoxy system have been investigated in a pultrusion process. The viscosity of resin was measured at various preheat temperatures for different times. A suitable range of viscosities of unsaturated polyester was found from 650 cps to 2500 cps. Reaction kinetics of resin and the heat transfer for different resin systems in pultrusion process were conducted by using a linear regression and a finite different method. The simulated results were compared with experimental data; both agree very well. Both kinetic data and resin temperature distribution will furnish process engineers with some useful information for practical application. However, more basic studies, e.g. resin reaction chemistry, interface of matrix and reinforcement, etc., shall be carried on to investigate the real-time processing parameters.

5. REFERENCE

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